

Bioremediation of Crude Oil Contaminated Soil Using Emulsifier, NPK Fertilizer and Microbial Agents, Near Kaduna Refinery

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 20 Nov 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Bioremediation Crude Oil Emulsifier NPK Fertilizer Microbial Agents</p>	<p>The objective of this research is to remediate soil contaminated with crude oil by utilizing an emulsifier, NPK fertilizer, and microbial agents sourced from the vicinity of Kaduna Refining and Petrochemical Company Limited (KRPC). Two distinct sets of soil samples were gathered near KRPC, designated as samples D and P. The experimental method employed was synthesis. Bioremediation was initiated and assessed by separately applying fertilizer (F), bacteria inoculation (B), and emulsifier (E) to the contaminated soil, as well as by combining bacteria inoculation with fertilizer (B and F), fertilizer with emulsifier (F and E), bacteria inoculation with emulsifier (B and E), and a combination of bacteria inoculation, emulsifier, and fertilizer (B, E, and F) on both samples D and P. The effectiveness of bioremediation was evaluated using the weight loss method over a treatment period of 28 days. The results indicated that the initial concentration of the contaminant (oil) was 398 g/kg for sample D and 194 g/kg for sample P. The pH levels of the soil were measured at 5.9 for sample D and 6.2 for sample P. The cation exchange capacity (CEC) was found to be greater in sample P compared to sample D, with values of 32.0 and 30.0 mmol/kg of soil, respectively. Sample P exhibited higher concentrations of cations (Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, K⁺, and Na⁺) with concentration values of 3.6, 1.17, 0.50, and 0.22 mol/kg, respectively. The findings revealed that the combination treatment of B, E, and F resulted in the highest percentage of oil degradation (97% for sample P and 95% for sample D), followed by treatment with B alone (96% for sample D and 81% for sample P).</p>

1. Introduction

Hydrocarbon contamination is one of the significant environmental challenges faced globally today, primarily due to activities associated with the petrochemical industry. Soil contaminated with petroleum poses risks to human health, contaminates groundwater, and diminishes agricultural productivity (Obruche et al., 2019).

The health issue arises mainly from direct exposure to contaminated soil, vapors emitted by the pollutants, and the secondary contamination of water sources within the soil. In Nigeria, challenges related to oil pollution have been widespread since the initiation of oil exploration and the development of the petroleum sector (Okoh & Trejo-Hernandez, 2006; Clark et al., 2025). The accidental discharge of petroleum products poses significant environmental risks. Hydrocarbon constituents are recognized as part of the group of carcinogens and neurotoxic organic pollutants. Presently accepted disposal techniques, such as incineration or burial in secure landfills, can become excessively costly when dealing with large quantities of contaminants (Umudi & Awatefe, 2018). Bioremediation is defined as the application of living microorganisms to mitigate environmental pollution. The long-term

objective of bioremediation strategies is to develop cost-effective solutions that reduce pollutants to a level deemed as low as reasonably achievable and practically possible (ALARP). The biodegradation of petroleum hydrocarbons is a multifaceted process influenced by the type and quantity of hydrocarbons present (Umudi, 2011). Mechanical and chemical techniques typically employed to extract hydrocarbons from contaminated locations exhibit limited efficacy and can incur high costs (Edema et al., 2009). Bioremediation represents a promising approach for addressing these contaminated sites, as it is economically viable and can result in complete mineralization. The fundamental principle of bioremediation is biodegradation, which may involve the total mineralization of organic pollutants into carbon dioxide, water, inorganic substances, and cellular proteins, or the transformation of complex organic pollutants into simpler organic compounds by biological agents such as microorganisms (Ekpo et al., 2025).

Numerous indigenous microorganisms found in water and soil possess the ability to degrade hydrocarbon contaminants. The bioremediation process, which is an emerging technique for detoxifying or eliminating pollutants, is increasingly recognized for its effectiveness in removing and degrading various environmental pollutants, including those resulting from the petroleum industry. It is widely believed that bioremediation technology is non-invasive and relatively cost-efficient (Erienu et al., 2022). The biodegradation carried out by natural populations of microorganisms is one of the key mechanisms through which petroleum and other hydrocarbon pollutants can be eliminated from the environment, and it is more economical than alternative remediation technologies (Obruche et al., 2025). A crucial requirement for the degradation of oil is the presence of microorganisms that possess the necessary metabolic capabilities. When these microorganisms are available, optimal growth rates and hydrocarbon biodegradation can be maintained by ensuring sufficient concentrations of nutrients and oxygen are present. Recently, Nigeria has experienced a significant increase in population, urbanization, and industrial activities (Ese et al., 2024). Pollution resulting from petroleum and its derivatives is the most common issue in the refinery environment in Nigeria. In the event of a major oil spill, the supply of carbon increases dramatically, while the availability of nitrogen and phosphorus typically becomes the limiting factor for oil degradation (Umudi et al., 2025), thus highlighting the necessity to enhance bioremediation efforts. Bioremediation presents several advantages over traditional methods such as landfilling or incineration. It can be performed on-site, is often more cost-effective, and causes minimal disruption to the site. Additionally, it permanently eliminates waste, reduces long-term liability, enjoys greater public acceptance, receives regulatory support, and can be integrated with other physical or chemical treatment methods (Essienn et al., 2010; Umudi, 2019).

The objective of this research is to achieve the bioremediation of soil contaminated with crude oil by utilizing an emulsifier, NPK fertilizer, and microbial agents, in proximity to the Kaduna refinery.

2. Materials and Method

2.1 Study Area

Kano State is located at a latitude of $11^{\circ} 07' N$ and a longitude of $07^{\circ} 42' E$, and it is currently recognized as one of the significant states in Northern Nigeria (Obruche et al., 2018; Umudi et al., 2022). The state encompasses a total area of 300 km^2 and comprises four primary settlements: Zaria City, Tudun Wada, Sabon Gari, and Samaru, which span across two local government areas: Sabon Gari and Zaria. This area is confronted with environmental sanitation challenges, including the improper disposal of waste near residential areas, which results in the contamination of underground water due to leachates from dumpsites, as numerous wells in close proximity to these locations are either poorly covered or left uncovered. The region experiences a tropical continental climate characterized by a pronounced dry season that lasts for up to seven months (from October to May). During the dry season, a cooler phase typically occurs between November and February, influenced by the northeastern winds (the harmattan) that impact the tropical continental air mass originating from the Sahara (Ese et al., 2024). This climatic pattern prevails in many regions of the country. In March and April, Kano State undergoes a brief period of hot yet dry weather, which is subsequently followed by a gradual arrival of tropical maritime air from the Atlantic Ocean that displaces the northeastern (Harmattan) winds. The rainy season lasts from May to September/October, with an average annual rainfall of 1040 mm distributed over approximately 90 rainy days (Obruche et al., 2019; Umudi et al., 2024).

Figure 1: Overview of Kaduna Refinery

2.2 Sample Location

The selected site for the experiment is the Kaduna refinery depots area located in Kaduna State, where a significant amount of oil effluent is discharged. Two distinct sets of samples were gathered in proximity to the Kaduna Refining and Petrochemical Company Limited (KRPC), a subsidiary of the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) in Kaduna (Latitude: $10^{\circ}25'18.81''$ and Longitude: $70^{\circ}29'14.63''$). The sampling locations were chosen due to their proximity to the areas where petroleum products are transferred into tanker trucks (Abeokuta et al., 2025).

2.3 Sample Collection

The method employed for sample collection was akin to that of WHO (2010) and Akpoveta et al. (2024), with some minor adjustments. The sampling strategy utilized in this research is the stratified method. The sampling area was segmented into sectors or quadrants, and a total of fifteen (15) samples were collected following the proportionality rule (i.e., obtaining more samples from regions with a higher concentration of contaminants). This approach was integrated with the composite method, which entails mixing sampling units to create a single sample (Festus-Amadi et al., 2021). The upper 2cm layer of the sample core was extracted and utilized for oil analysis using a sterilized spatula. The first set of samples, designated as (D), was sourced from locations where diesel from the refinery had spilled into the environment, while the second set, labeled (P), was collected from areas where petrol had leaked and spilled. To prevent cross-contamination or any chemical and biological alterations in the samples, clean and appropriate PVC bags, tin cans, and sampling bottles were employed for storage.

2.4 Sample Preparation

The preparation method utilized was based on the process outlined by WHO (2010), Mughele et al. (2024), and Erienu et al. (2022). Samples were prepared by manually removing dirt, stones, and iron, then air-dried and sieved using 2mm sieves prior to the analysis of physicochemical parameters.

2.5 Cultured Medium Preparation

The methods for preparing the cultured medium were akin to those described by Othman (2001) and Onder et al. (2007). The medium utilized for culturing the sample was a blood agar base. To prepare the medium, 40g of blood agar was weighed and added to 1000 ml of distilled water in a volumetric flask, then heated to dissolve. It was sterilized at 121°C for 15 minutes, after which 20 ml was poured into a Petri dish and allowed to cool and solidify, as per the manufacturer's instructions.

2.6 Sample Culturing

The method for culturing the sample was similar to that of Ogwuche C.E. and Obruche E.K. (2020), with a few minor modifications. A sample weighing 0.1g was placed into a sterile test tube containing 10ml of normal saline (0.8g of normal salt in 10ml of distilled water) and mixed thoroughly. A loopful of the sample from the normal saline was sub-cultured onto a plate of the prepared medium (blood agar), where it was smeared and streaked across the surface. The incubation of the cultured medium was performed anaerobically by placing the sample in an anaerobic jar and using a gas pack kit to generate carbon dioxide, at a temperature of 37°C for 48 hours. Following this, the cultured medium was examined for bacterial colony growth and morphology, including size and color. The bacterial colonies were subjected to Gram staining, and the Gram reaction of the colonies was assessed.

2.7 Gram Staining

The Gram staining method employed was based on the procedure outlined by Onwerenmadu et al. (2007) and WHO (2010), with some modifications. The Gram staining process involved selecting a colony of bacteria, which was then smeared onto a glass slide, air-dried, and heat-fixed. This slide was placed on the staining rack in a sink, flooded with crystal violet, and allowed to stand for 1 minute before being washed with water. It was then flooded with Gram's iodine and allowed to stand for another minute, followed by another wash with water. The slide was decolorized with ethanol for 10 seconds, washed with water again, and subsequently counterstained with safranin for 30 seconds. Finally, it was washed with water and blotted dry using filter paper. This observation was conducted using a microscope with oil immersion magnification (x100) to assess the Gram reaction, cellular shape, and arrangement. The biochemical activities of the colonies were evaluated, specifically oxidase and catalase tests.

2.8 Physicochemical Analysis

The physicochemical analysis method employed was based on the procedure outlined by Osuji and Chukwunedum (2001) and WHO (2010). This analysis focused on determining moisture content, pH, total nitrogen, Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC), Chloride, Carbonate, Bicarbonate, Organic Carbon, and Phosphorus.

2.9 Determination of Exchangeable Bases (Mg, Ca, K, and Na)

The sample collection techniques were akin to those described by Umudi et al. (2025), with minor adjustments. A 10g sample of soil, sieved to 2 mm, was placed into a funnel positioned over 100 ml volumetric flasks. The soil was leached with a 1M ammonium acetate solution to a total volume of 100 ml, with leaching conducted for approximately 2 hours, using about 10 ml of acetate for each wash. After leaching, the funnel was removed, and the flask was corked and shaken thoroughly. Sodium (Na) and Potassium (K) concentrations were determined using flame emission, while Calcium (Ca) and Magnesium (Mg) were analyzed via atomic absorption spectrometry on the leachate.

2.10 Biodegradation of Crude Oil

The preparation method utilized was based on the process described by WHO (2010) and Umudi et al. (2025). The quantity of crude oil degraded in each soil sample was assessed using the weight loss method established by Bossert and Bartha (1984). This involved suspending 3g of soil in 10ml of diethyl ether within a universal bottle and shaking vigorously to extract the oil. The solvent-oil mixture was then carefully transferred into a pre-weighed beaker. This extraction process was repeated until all oil was removed from the soil. The solvent-oil mixture was left at room temperature overnight to ensure complete evaporation of the solvent. The new weight of the beaker containing the residual oil was taken and the percentage of oil degraded calculated (Itodo et al., 2021).

$$\% \text{ of oil degraded} = \frac{\text{original oil concentration} - \text{final oil concentration}}{\text{original oil concentration}} \times 100$$

The initial oil concentration refers to the original concentration of oil (measured as the weight of extracted oil in g/g) that is determined prior to any treatment being applied to the contaminated soil. In contrast, the final oil concentration is defined as the concentration of oil extracted on days 7, 14, 21, and 28 following the application of treatment to the contaminated soil (also measured in g/g).

Figure 2: Sample degradation process

2.11 Statistical Tool

A straightforward T-test analysis was conducted to assess the significant difference in the oil degradation trend between samples P and D after: (1) inoculation with *Bacillus* sp, (2) the addition of an emulsifier along with *Bacillus* sp inoculation, and (3) the addition of fertilizer, emulsifier, and *Bacillus* sp inoculation, utilizing IBM SPSS Statistics.

3. Results and Discussion

This section provides the analyzed results concerning the degradation of crude oil from soil using an emulsifier, NPK fertilizer, and microbial agents, specifically from samples near the Kaduna refinery, as depicted in Tables 1-6.

3.1 Physicochemical Properties of Soil

The findings from the physicochemical analysis of the contaminated soils presented in Table 1 indicate that the soil texture is sandy, with a pH value ranging from 5.9 to 6.2. This aligns with the findings of Osuji and Chukwunedum (2001), who conducted similar research at the same sampling site. The pH range is optimal for bioremediation, as it falls within the necessary range of 5.5 to 8.8 for microbial growth and activity, thus negating the need for pH adjustment prior to treatment. The observed reduction in pH value in this study may be attributed to the increased concentration of contaminants and the nature of the contaminants themselves. The organic content in the samples was found to average 28.30 g/kg for sample D and 37.00 g/kg for sample P, in contrast to the 14.67 g/kg reported by Ekpo et al. (2023) for a control site (a non-oil contaminated site) within the Kaduna metropolis. Additionally, the Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC) values were recorded at 30.0 and 32.0 mmol/kg for samples D and P, respectively, compared to the reported value of 13.07 mmol/kg. The elevated percentage of organic carbon content in the study sites is likely due to oil spillage, which primarily consists of hydrocarbons. The CEC of soils is influenced by the nature and quality of the soil as well as the organic carbon content. Therefore, the high percentage of organic carbon in these sites could account for the elevated CEC values. All study sites exhibited a mean cation exchange capacity that was comparatively higher than the mean CEC of 8.14 mmol/kg reported by Umudi et al. (2025). The samples showed average moisture content of 0.5% for sample D and 1.25% for sample P, respectively. Higher CEC typically indicates a greater presence of organic matter in the soil; soils with high CEC generally possess a greater water holding capacity compared to those with low CEC. This observation aligns with the findings presented in Table 1, where the high CEC in sample P correlates with a higher percentage of moisture content when compared to sample D. Soils characterized by low CEC are more susceptible to deficiencies in potassium (K^+), magnesium (Mg^{2+}), and other cations. The incorporation of organic matter can enhance the CEC of soil, although this process may take many years to manifest. Sample P demonstrates a higher CEC, resulting in a greater concentration of cations (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , K^+ , and Na^+ with values of 3.6, 1.17, 0.50, and 0.22 mol/kg, respectively), whereas sample D, with a lower CEC, exhibits a reduced concentration of cations (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , K^+ , and Na^+ with values of 1.20, 0.27, 0.25, and 0.17 mol/kg, respectively). This suggests that the concentration of soil minerals is influenced by the discharge of hydrocarbons into the soil. The total nitrogen concentration in the samples was measured at 3.30 mg/kg for sample D and 10.50 mg/kg for sample P. Additionally, the phosphorus concentration was found to be 1.33 mg/kg for sample D and 11.36 mg/kg for sample P. These levels provide sufficient nutrients for microbial growth. The elevated concentrations of nitrogen and phosphorus in sample P are likely to facilitate the natural degradation of contaminants, as phosphorus and nitrogen serve as nutrients for microbes, thereby bio-stimulating the existing indigenous organisms.

Table 1: Measured Physicochemical Parameters of Soil Samples

Parameters	Contaminated with Diesel(D)	Contaminated with Petrol (P)
Moisturecontent (%)	0.50	1.25
Sand(g/kg)	940	900
Silt (g/kg)	20	60
Clay(g/kg)	40	40
Textural class	Sand	Sand
pH	5.9	6.2
Organiccontent (g/kg)	28.30	37.00
Nitrogen (g/kg)	3.30	10.50
Availablephosphorus (mg/kg)	1.33	11.36
Calcium(cmol/kg)	1.20	3.60
Magnesium(cmol/kg)	0.27	1.17
Potassium (cmol/kg)	0.25	0.50
Sodium (cmol/kg)	0.17	0.22
CEC (cmol/kg)	3.00	3.20
Carbonate(mg/kg)	0.00	0.00
Bicarbonate(mg/kg)	0.80	1.20
Chloride(mg/kg)	0.60	0.80

3.2 The Percentage of Oil (Contaminant) Degraded Over Time

Table 1 to 2 illustrates the extent of oil (contaminant) degradation in soil samples (D and P), represented in percentages over time when treated with bacteria, emulsified with liquid soap, and enhanced by the addition of NPK fertilizer, both separately and in combination. These findings were derived from measuring the weight loss of oil over time. Additionally, Table 1 presents the percentage of oil degradation over time in the control sample (D without treatment). The initial concentration of the sample was established, and after 7 days, 3% of the initial concentration was degraded. Seven days later, it was observed that 58% of the oil concentration had degraded, and after a total of 14 days, the rate of oil degradation significantly slowed. A related study conducted by Ukpong and Peter (2012) reported comparable results in the same region.

Table 2: Percentage (%) oil degraded with time in sample D

Days	F	B	F&B	B&E	B,E&F	E&F	E	C
7	20	7	23	3	5	12	13	3
14	56	88	45	68	50	56	61	58
21	58	94	63	72	63	63	64	59
28	59	95	64	73	95	77	65	60

Table 3: Percentage (%) of oil degraded oil with time in sample P

DAYS	B	E	B &E	B, E &F	C
Day 7	7	2	6	20	3
Day 14	60	73	88	84	58
Day 21	64	88	89	90	59
Day 28	81	89	89	97	60

Table 2 illustrates the percentage of oil degradation in sample D over time, utilizing Bacillus sp and NPK fertilizer (E and F). On day 7, the oil degradation concentration is recorded at 12%, which rises to 56% by day 14, and further increases to 77% by day 28. Additionally, Table 2 presents the percentage of oil degradation over time for sample D when inoculated with Bacillus sp and supplemented with NPK fertilizer (B and F). On day 7, the oil degradation concentration reaches 23%, marking the highest concentration observed on that day across all experimental groups. By day 14, this percentage rises to 45%, and by day 21, it further escalates to 63%, after which no significant degradation is noted. Furthermore, Tables 2 and 3 depict the percentage of oil degradation over time for samples D and P, respectively, treated with an emulsifier, NPK fertilizer, and inoculated with Bacillus sp (B, E, and F). In Table 2 (sample D), the oil degradation concentration after 7 days is 5%, which increases to 50% by day 14, and further rises to 95% after 28 days. In Table 3 (sample P), the oil degradation concentration on day 7 is 20%, which increases to 84% by day 14, and further escalates to 97% by day 28. Uboh et al. (2011) and Udosen et al. (2012) share similar perspectives in their findings regarding the analysis of bioremediation at the Unenurhie dumpsite.

Table 4: Percentage (%) of oil degraded from the samples (D and P) using bacteria combined with emulsifier

Days	P	D
7	6	5
14	88	68
21	89	72
28	89	80

Table 4 illustrates the percentage of oil degradation from the sample sets (D and P, respectively) over time when emulsified and inoculated with *Bacillus* sp (B and E). In the same Table 4, it is noted that 3% of the oil was degraded on day 7, and by day 14, this percentage rose to 68%, with a slight increase to 72% by day 21. Additionally, in the same Table 4, the concentration of oil degraded on day 7 was recorded at 6%, which increased to 88% on day 14. Following this, no significant degradation was observed. These findings align excellently with those previously reported by Umanah et al. (2025), who documented similar results.

Table 5: Percentage (%) of oil degraded using bacteria only on D and P

DAYS	P	D
Day7	7	7
Day14	60	88
Day21	65	94
Day28	81	95

Table 5 illustrates the percentage of oil degradation over time when sample sets are inoculated solely with *Bacillus* sp (B) for samples P and D, respectively. In Table 5 (inoculation of P with bacteria), 7% of the oil was degraded after 7 days of inoculation, and after an additional 7 days, the percentage of oil degraded rose to 60%. This significant increase in degradation further escalated to 64% after another 7 days, ultimately reaching 81%. Conversely, in the same Table 5 (inoculation of D with bacteria), 7% of the oil was degraded after 7 days, and after another 7 days, the percentage surged to 88%. Following an additional 7 days, the percentage increased to 94%, after which there was no further increase in oil degradation. These findings align with the research conducted by Umudi et al. (2025) and Udosen et al. (2012).

Table 6: Percentage (%) of oil degraded from the samples (P and D) using bacteria combine with fertilizer and emulsifier

DAYS	P	D
7	2	3
14	89	50
21	90	63
28	97	95

Table 2 & 3 illustrate the comparison of the degradation rate trends of oil in samples P and D when inoculated with *Bacillus* sp. On day 7, both samples exhibited a 7% degradation of their contaminants. By day 14, the degradation in sample P rose to 88%, while sample D only reached 60%, which later increased to 65%. In contrast, sample P further escalated to 94%. During the final week of the experiment, the degradation rate in sample P was slow, ranging from 94% to 95%, whereas sample D experienced a significant increase from 65% to 81%. The degradation trends in samples D and P were significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Table 2 & 3 also compare the degradation rate trends of oil in samples P and D when inoculated with *Bacillus* sp and Emulsified (B and E). A statistical difference ($P < 0.05$) was observed in the degradation trends between D and P, despite their nearly identical percentages after 28 days (97% and 95%, respectively). Udo (2006) shared a similar perspective in their findings regarding bioremediation analysis in the Agbarho oil field.

4. Conclusion

This research concludes that, within the limits of experimental error and estimations, enhanced bioremediation results can be achieved by refining conventional bioremediation methods (bioaugmentation and biostimulation) through the addition of emulsifiers. The degradation trend is summarized as follows: (B, E and F) > B > (B and E) > (E and F) > (B and F) > E > F. Furthermore, this study demonstrated that significant degradation occurred after 14 days of treatment.

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